

REDUCTION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS IN THE WIND TURBINE SYSTEM THROUGH THE USE OF OFF-AXIS PLYS IN THE SPAR CAPS OF COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADES

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Keywords: Damage equivalent load, Fatigue life, Wind turbine, Bending-twisting coupling

ABSTRACT

In the wind turbine industry, as the requirements for fatigue life and reliability increase, to achieve these goals appropriate measures must be taken such that loads incurred due to the flexing of the blades must be alleviated. In this study, the use of different off-axis ply angles in the main spar caps of wind turbine blades is investigated for its effectiveness in reducing fatigue damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system. To achieve load alleviation in the wind turbine system, bending-twisting coupling in composite blades, generated by the use of off-axis plies in the spar caps of the blades, is exploited. Study is conducted utilizing both linear and non-linear blade models in the multi-body models of the 5MW wind turbine system that are set up in two separate wind turbine multi-body dynamic codes increase the reliability of the conclusions drawn from the analyses. Transient aeroelastic analyses of the wind turbine system are performed for the power production load case using the normal turbulence model as the external wind loading. Time history results of simulations are used to calculate damage equivalent loads at the selected monitor points in the wind turbine system. The use of CFRP material in the main spar caps of the bend-twist coupled blade is specifically investigated for its effectiveness in reducing damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system. Results show that with the introduction of off-axis spar cap plies in the blades, reductions in the damage equivalent loads can be achieved in the wind turbine system compared to baseline design, and reduction in fatigue damage equivalent loads in the wind turbine system is higher when the bending-twisting coupling is increased through the use of higher fiber angle in the spar cap plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the wind turbine industry, as the requirements for fatigue life and reliability increase, to achieve these goals appropriate measures must be taken such that loads incurred due to the flexing of the blades must be alleviated. For wind turbine systems which have power output in the megawatt range, reducing the fatigue loads is very crucial to keep the turbine system operational for longer durations to increase the productivity. Fatigue damage equivalent load is a sign of the degradation of the components of the wind turbine system due to material fatigue resulting from cyclic loading. Damage

equivalent load can be used as the metric to compare the fatigue performance of different designs. Reduction in the damage equivalent loads implies increased fatigue life of the structural elements.

In the literature there has been studies in utilizing passive mechanisms to control load in the wind turbine systems. In many studies, 5 MW wind turbine system of NREL [1] is used as a reference turbine to demonstrate the implementation of load reduction methodologies. Zhou and Wang [2] used the blade of NREL's 5 MW wind turbine system as the baseline blade and have shown by finite element analysis that by using different composite material with different fiber orientations in the blades, bending-twisting coupling characteristics of the blade can be changed appreciably. Lin and Lai [3] adopted a combined analytical and finite element beam model to study the elastic coupling in wind turbine blades. Their results showed that mixed-use of carbon and glass fibers can provide better coupling properties, and concluded that blade developers should arrange the off-axis fibers to adapt to the operating conditions in order to reach better performance. Lobitz et al. [4] showed that the incorporation of twist-coupled blades in rotor design can be beneficial to energy production or load reduction, and possibly both simultaneously. In their study, for reducing loads, the blades are designed to twist toward feather as they bend and their study showed that for variable speed pitch-controlled rotors, twist coupling substantially decreases fatigue damage over all wind speeds, without reducing average power. Capellaro studied the bending-twisting coupling effect on the internal loads in wind blades [5]. In his work, Capellaro adopted the 5 MW wind turbine of NREL turbine as the baseline turbine. His study showed that as a result of bending-twisting coupling generated with the use of off-axis plies in the spar caps of the wind turbine blade, reduction in the damage equivalent blade root bending and torsional moments could be possible. Gözcü et al. [6] presented the inverse design methodology of the blade of 5 MW NREL wind turbine blade and investigated the effect of off-axis spar cap plies on damage equivalent loads in wind turbines with superelement blade definition. Because superelement blades have the whole coupling effects, the effect of off-axis spar cap plies on the wind turbine performance and internal loads in the whole wind turbine system could be studied. Gözcü et al. [7] performed a comparative study of wind turbine simulation with superelement blades and geometrically nonlinear beam blades. This study showed that superelement blade could be used in the multi-body dynamic model of the wind turbine system for the study of the effect of bending-twisting coupling on the load alleviation in the wind turbine system. It is concluded that with the introduction of bending-twisting coupling, damage equivalent loads could be reduced in the critical connection points in the whole wind turbine system, and not just in the blades. In a follow-up study Gözcü et al. [8] investigated use of hybrid GFRP-CFRP material in wind turbine blades for its effectiveness in reducing fatigue damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system, and comparisons are made against the baseline full GFRP blade in terms of strength, deformation, dynamic characteristics, weight and cost of the blade. It is shown that in the overall, with the introduction of off-axis CFRP spar cap plies in the blades, higher reductions in the damage equivalent loads could be achieved in wind turbine systems compared to the use of full GFRP in the main spar caps of the blade.

Present study is a follow-up study of Gözcü et al. [8]. In the previous studies of the authors, only the effect of 15° off-axis spar cap ply placement on the bending-twisting coupling potential of the blade and on the reduction of the damage equivalent loads were studied. In this study, the effect lower off-axis spar cap ply angle on the reduction of fatigue damage equivalent loads is also investigated. It should be noted that bending-twisting coupling potential of blades can be modified through the use of different off-axis ply angles and by changing the application region of the off-axis plies in the main spar caps of the blades. In this study, application region of the off-axis plies in the main spar caps of the blades is kept as same as in the previous studies of the authors [6-8]. Off-axis plies are placed in the main pressure and suction side spar caps in the 30 m of the blade measured from the blade tip. The effect of both 5° and 15° off-axis spar cap ply placement on the reduction of fatigue damage equivalent loads is investigated by utilizing both linear and non-linear blade models in the multi-body model of the wind turbine system. To conduct the study, 5 MW multi-body wind turbine models are established in two separate wind turbine multi-body dynamic codes, Samcef Wind Turbine (SWT) [9] and PHATAS [10]. Transient aeroelastic analyses of the wind turbine system are performed with the multi-body codes SWT and PHATAS for the power production load case and the normal turbulence model as the external wind loading. Transient analyses are performed for a duration of 10 minutes, as specified in IEC 61400-1. Time history results are used to calculate damage equivalent loads in the

root of the blade and in the drive train of the wind turbine system. The use of CFRP material in the main spar caps of the blade is specifically investigated for its effectiveness in reducing fatigue damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system, and comparisons are made with the use of full GFRP in the blade in terms of reduction in damage equivalent loads in the wind turbine. It is shown by SWT and PHATAS simulations that in the overall, with the introduction of off-axis spar cap plies in the blades, reductions in the damage equivalent loads can be achieved in the wind turbine system compared to baseline design having on-axis GFRP plies in the main spar caps of the turbine blade.

2 DEFINITION OF THE REFERENCE WIND TURBINE

The effect of off-axis spar cap plies on the reduction of fatigue damage equivalent loads in the wind turbine is studied using the multi-body models of the 5 MW reference wind turbine that are created SWT and PHATAS. Although SWT and PHATAS do not have the same sub-component definitions, special care is given to build almost similar wind turbine systems in SWT and PHATAS. To build the reference wind turbine, some of the known properties of NREL's 5 MW turbine [1] are taken as reference. Figure 1 shows the reference wind turbine model established in SWT and Table 1 gives the main properties of the reference wind turbine set up in SWT and PHATAS.

Figure 1: Multi-body model of the wind turbine system established in SWT

Nominal power	5 MW
Number of blades	3
Number of blade elements used in SWT and PHATAS	17
Blade prebent at the tip	4m
Rated rotor speed	12 RPM
Demanded rated generator torque	37880 Nm
Wind speed at hub height	15 m/s
Turbulent wind generator used in SWT	TURBSIM [11]
Turbulent wind generator used in PHATAS	SWIFT [12]
Gearbox ratio	105
Rotor/Hub diameter	126 m / 4 m
Hub length	4 m
Blade length	61.5 m
Rotor conicity	0 degree
Rotor tilt angle	5 degree
Tower centerline elevation	98.2 m
Hub height	100 m
Hub mass	50,000 kg
Hub inertia	100000 kgm ²
Control (SWT)	PI pitch position control
Control (PHATAS)	PD pitch speed control
Control increment in SWT and PHATAS	0.01 s

Table 1: Main properties of the reference wind turbine established in SWT and PHATAS

For the multi-body simulation of the wind turbine system performed in PHATAS coupled beam models and for the multi-body simulation of the wind turbine system performed in SWT dynamic superelement blade models are used. To build coupled beam and superelement blade models, a three dimensional reference blade is needed. Design of the three dimensional model of the blade is based on the inverse design methodology performed by Gözcü et al. [6]. As described in detail by Gözcü et al. [6], inverse design of the three dimensional blade is performed such that sectional beam properties of the reference 3D blade approximately match the sectional beam properties of NREL's 5 MW turbine blade [1]. In the reference turbine blade, GFRP is used as the base material in the spar cap and shell regions of the blade. Baseline blade has full GFRP material with 0° fiber orientation angle (θ) in the main spar caps. Zero degree orientation is defined as the axis which traverses the blade from blade root to the blade tip through the middle of the spar caps as shown in Figure 2. Stiffness and mass properties of the beam models used in PHATAS simulations are calculated by the variational asymptotic beam section (VABS) code [13]. For SWT simulations dynamic superelement used is a non-linear superelement that is based on the Craig and Bampton component mode method. Nonlinearities arise from the fact that formulation of the superelement allows modeling of the blade structure undergoing large displacements and rotations in space associated with the rigid body rotation of the blade, with the only limitation that with respect to the local frame fixed to the blade, blade behaves geometrically linear. Figure 2 also shows the spar cap region with off-axis plies. In the bend-twist coupled beams, off-axis spar cap plies are placed in the main pressure and suction side spar caps in the 30 m of the blade measured from the blade tip. To generate the required bending-twisting coupling, off-axis plies are oriented towards the leading edge of the blade. In the current study, off-axis ply angles are taken as 5° and 15° and the effect of off-axis spar cap plies on the reduction of fatigue damage equivalent loads is studied by making comparisons with damage equivalent loads obtained from the multi-body simulations of the the reference wind turbine with the reference blade.

Figure 2: Wind turbine blade design showing the spar cap region with off-axis plies; $\theta = 5^\circ, 15^\circ$

3 WIND TURBINE SIMULATIONS AND CALCULATION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS

Multi-body simulations of the wind turbine systems in Samcef Wind Turbine and PHATAS are performed for the power production load case and turbulent wind conditions. In the multi-body simulations, normal turbulence model as the external wind loading, as specified in IEC 61400-1. Wind speed at the reference height is taken as 15 m/s with a wind shear factor of 0.2, and in case of normal turbulence wind condition, Kaimal turbulence model is used for the generation of aerodynamic loading. In the turbulent wind analyses, IEC wind turbine class is taken as 1 and turbulence class is selected as B. Transient aeroelastic analyses are performed for a duration of 10 minutes.

Damage equivalent load is used as the metric to compare the fatigue performance of the components of the wind turbine with the baseline blade design with the fatigue performance of the components of the wind turbine with bend-twist coupled blade designs. Damage equivalent load is calculated using Eq. (1) which is derived based on the assumption that fatigue loads (F) are related with number of load cycles (N) such that the product $F^m N$ is constant and in the Miner's rule, damage term is taken as 1 which indicates the occurrence of the fatigue failure. In Eq. (1), N_{ref} is the reference number of cycles taken as 10^8 , m is the fatigue exponent with typical values in the range 3-10 depending on the material system, and F_i is the internal load corresponding to i^{th} bin with n_i being the number of fatigue load cycles corresponding to i^{th} bin. If damage equivalent loads are calculated using Eq. (1) for two different load spectra, then the ratio of the damage equivalent loads, calculated for two different load spectra, become independent of the reference number of cycles N_{ref} .

$$F_{ref} = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (F_i^m n_i) / N_{ref}}{m} \right)^{1/m} \quad (1)$$

Table 2 introduces the baseline GFRP and baseline hybrid GFRP and CFRP blade designs and bend-twist coupled blades designs. These designs are used to study the effect of bending-twisting coupling due to off-axis spar cap plies in turbine blades on the reduction of fatigue damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system. In this study, the off-axis ply angle θ is taken as 5° and 15° .

Blades	Description
GFRP_1	Baseline GFRP blade with pressure/suction side GFRP spar cap plies along the blade axis (0 deg.) in the outboard 30 m of the blade.
HGCFRP_1	Baseline hybrid GFRP and CFRP blade with pressure/suction side CFRP spar cap plies along the blade axis (0 deg.) in the outboard 30 m of the blade. Note: Number of CFRP layers in the sections of the outboard 30 m of blade is adjusted such that these sections have very close flapwise bending stiffness compared to the flapwise bending stiffness of GFRP_1.
GFRP_2	Coupled GFRP blade with pressure/suction side GFRP spar cap plies oriented at θ deg. towards the leading edge in the outboard 30 m of the blade. Note: 0 deg. plies of GFRP_1 are made θ deg.
HGCFRP_2	Coupled hybrid GFRP and CFRP blade with pressure/suction side CFRP spar cap plies oriented at θ deg. towards the leading edge in the outboard 30 m of the blade. Note: 0 deg. plies of HGCFRP_1 are made θ deg.
HGCFRP_3	Coupled hybrid GFRP and CFRP blade with pressure/suction side spar cap plies composed of CFRP spar cap plies oriented at θ deg. towards the leading edge in the outboard 30 m of the blade. Note: Number of CFRP layers in the sections of the outboard 30 m of blade is adjusted such that these sections have very close flapwise bending stiffness compared to the flapwise bending stiffness of GFRP_2.
HGCFRP_5	Coupled hybrid GFRP and CFRP blade with pressure/suction side spar cap plies composed of GFRP and CFRP spar cap plies oriented at θ deg. towards the leading edge in the outboard 30 m of the blade. Note: 2/3 of the total number of GFRP layers in the sections of the outboard 30 m of GFRP_1 is made θ deg. and 1/3 of the total number of GFRP layers in GFRP_1 is modified to CFRP at θ deg. CFRP layers are placed in the outermost plies.

Table 2: Blade designs

Figure 3 shows the turbulent downwind velocity that is used by SWT and PHATAS. Figure 3(a) shows the turbulent wind profile generated by Turbsim and used in wind turbine simulations performed by SWT. Figure 3(b) shows the turbulent wind profile generated by Swift and used in wind turbine simulations performed by PHATAS. It should be noted that although very similar wind turbines are set up in SWT and PHATAS, it is not possible to compare the damage equivalent loads calculated by SWT and PHATAS quantitatively because of the differences in the simulation parameters used by SWT and PHATAS. Turbulent wind profiles used by SWT and PHATAS are generated internally by these codes and the differences in the wind profiles directly affect the fatigue loads in the wind turbine system. Besides the turbulent wind profile, differences between the SWT and PHATAS in the definition of the controllers, drive trains, blade models (beam and superelement) all affect the fatigue loads directly.

(a) Turbsim generated profile used by SWT (b) Swift generated profile used by PHATAS
 Figure 3: 10 minute long turbulent windprofiles used in wind turbine simulations

4 RESULTS ON THE EFFECT OF OFF-AXIS PLYS ON THE FATIGUE DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS

Transient aeroelastic analyses of the wind turbine systems are performed for the wind turbines having blade configurations described in Table 2. Transient aeroelastic analysis in SWT and PHATAS are performed at the mean wind speed of 15 m/s for a duration of 10 minutes. For the baseline GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP blades, off-axis spar cap ply angles are taken as 0° , and for the bend-twist coupled blades, off-axis spar cap ply angles are taken as 5° and 15° . Time history results of multi-body simulations of the wind turbine are used to calculate damage equivalent loads at the selected monitor points in the wind turbine system. An example of the effect of off-axis spar cap plies on the reduction in the flapwise bending moment in the critical section of the blade is shown in Figure 4. Results given in Fig.4 are PHATAS results obtained for wind turbines with the baseline GFRP blade GFRP_1 and the bend-twist coupled blade GFRP_2. Time history results clearly show that because of the reduction in the lift due to bend-twist coupling, reduction in the flapwise bending moment occurs in the critical section of the bend-twist coupled blade.

Figure 4: Time history of flapwise bending moment at the critical blade section – PHATAS results

Tables 3-6 present the fatigue damage equivalent loads calculated at the root of the blade. For the bend-twist coupled blades, damage equivalent loads are calculated with respect to the reference blade GFRP_1 which has 0° GFRP spar cap plies that are oriented along the blade axis. Fatigue damage equivalent loads are calculated using 1000 bins and fatigue exponent is taken as 4 assuming that metallic hub where the blades are connected at the blade root are evaluated for the fatigue damage.

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) blade root loads	Leadwise Moment (Nm)	207644	208242	168440	168965	3812
	Flapwise Moment (Nm)	125525	120715	118399	118585	11531
	Flapwise Shear Force (N)	3856.4	3760	3657.5	3665	202637
	Leadwise Shear Force (N)	11653	11672	10665	10781	124285
Ratio of DEL DE Bend-twist	Leadwise Moment		1.00	0.81	0.81	0.98
	Flapwise Moment		0.96	0.94	0.94	0.99
DE GFRP_1	Flapwise Shear Force		0.97	0.95	0.95	0.99
	Leadwise Shear Force		1.00	0.92	0.93	0.99

Table 3: Damage equivalent blade root loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta=5^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) blade root loads	Leadwise Moment (Nm)	207644	209777	171564	175678	204510
	Flapwise Moment (Nm)	125525	111356	104138	110440	113249
	Flapwise Shear Force (N)	3856.4	3566	3386.03	3552.7	3600.6
	Leadwise Shear Force (N)	11653	11716	10748.8	10853.8	11582.6
Ratio of DEL DE Bend-twist	Leadwise Moment		1.01	0.83	0.85	0.94
	Flapwise Moment		0.89	0.83	0.88	0.92
DE GFRP_1	Flapwise Shear Force		0.92	0.88	0.92	0.94
	Leadwise Shear Force		1.01	0.92	0.93	0.97

Table 4: Damage equivalent blade root loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta=15^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) blade root loads	Leadwise Moment (Nm)	366448	365757	365842	365665	364807
	Flapwise Moment (Nm)	394307	360592	324930	327453	321187
	Flapwise Shear Force (N)	12565	11776	10982	11057	11792
	Leadwise Shear Force (N)	20537	20526	20561	20553	20513
Ratio of DEL DE Bend-twist	Leadwise Moment		0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Flapwise Moment		0.91	0.82	0.83	0.92
DE GFRP_1	Flapwise Shear Force		0.93	0.87	0.88	0.93
	Leadwise Shear Force		0.99	1.00	1.00	0.99

Table 5: Damage equivalent blade root loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (PHATAS results / $\theta=5^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) blade root loads	Leadwise Moment (Nm)	366448	365352	365172	365046	364807
	Flapwise Moment (Nm)	394307	325096	275316	289641	321187
	Flapwise Shear Force (N)	12565	10995	9737	10137	10854
	Leadwise Shear Force (N)	20537	20521	20581	20562	20498
Ratio of DEL DE Bend-twist	Leadwise Moment		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Flapwise Moment		0.82	0.70	0.73	0.81
DE GFRP_1	Flapwise Shear Force		0.88	0.77	0.81	0.86
	Leadwise Shear Force		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 6: Damage equivalent blade root loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades^b – (PHATAS results / $\theta=15^\circ$)

For the blade root fatigue damage equivalent loads obtained by SWT, comparison of Tables 3 and 4 show that for the flapwise shear force and bending moment, increase in the off-axis fiber angle in the main spar caps from 5° to 15° results in higher reduction in fatigue damage equivalent loads. Significant decreases in the damage equivalent flapwise shear force and flapwise bending moment is a consequence of the reduction in the lift in the bend-twist coupled sections in the outboard 30 m of the blade. It is also seen that damage equivalent leadwise shear force and bending moment are not affected significantly by the fiber angle of the off-axis spar cap plies. For the wind turbine system with bend-twist coupled GFRP blades (GFRP_2), no reduction in the leadwise shear force and the leadwise bending moment is achieved by the use of either 5° or 15° off-axis spar cap plies. Tables 3 and 4 also show that for the wind turbine systems with hybrid GFRP and CFRP blades, damage equivalent blade root leadwise bending moments and leadwise blade root shear forces all have substantial reductions compared to the wind turbine systems with the baseline blade GFRP_1 and the bend-twist coupled GFRP_2. PHATAS results of damage equivalent blade root loads of wind turbines with bend-twist coupled blades are presented in Tables 5 and 6. PHATAS results show higher reductions in flapwise shear force and bending moment compared to SWT results. On the other hand, no decrease or increase in the damage equivalent blade root leadwise shear force and bending moment is obtained in PHATAS simulations. However in the overall, both SWT and PHATAS simulations show that substantial reductions in fatigue damage equivalent loads in the blade root loads is possible through the use of either full GFRP or hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades in the wind turbine system. In general, higher reductions in damage equivalent loads are obtained with hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades compared to full GFRP blades and with the use of higher off-axis fiber angle.

Tables 7-10 summarize the damage equivalent loads calculated by SWT at the main bearing 1 and main shaft gearbox connection points of the wind turbine systems with bend-twist coupled blades having 5° and 15° fiber angles in the main spar caps. From Tables 7 and 8, it is seen that substantial reductions in the damage equivalent main bearing 1 loads can be achieved with the use of off-axis spar cap plies in the blades. It is noted that the reduction in the damage equivalent axial force x is the highest. Axial force x is related to the thrust force component of the lift force acting on the blades, and the reduction in damage equivalent axial force x in main bearing 1 is substantial due to the reduction of the lift. In general, higher reductions in main bearing 1 loads can be achieved in wind turbines having bend-twist coupled blades with 15° fiber angles in the main spar caps compared to the 5° spar cap ply case. Except for the shaft torque, which is shown by moment x in Tables 9 and 10, higher reductions in damage equivalent gear box connection loads can be also be achieved with the use of higher off-axis spar cap ply angle in the blades. It is noted that the shaft torque is a result of collection of leadwise root bending moment of the three blades plus the additional moment due to the leadwise blade root shear force with respect to the hub center. Tables 3 and 4 show that for wind turbines with hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades, damage equivalent blade root leadwise bending moments and leadwise blade root shear forces all have substantial reductions compared to the wind turbine with baseline blade GFRP_1. However, damage equivalent shaft torque of wind turbines with hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades is still higher than the damage equivalent shaft torque of the wind turbine with the baseline blade. The reason for the higher damage equivalent shaft torque for the hybrid GFRP and CFRP blades is still not understood. SWT simulations also show that when the fiber angle of the spar cap plies is increased, damage equivalent shaft torque also increases.

Tables 11 and 12 give PHATAS simulation results of damage equivalent rotor shaft and drive train loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades for spar cap fiber angles of 5° and 15° , respectively. Table 12 shows that except for the wind turbine with the blade configuration HGCFRP_2, substantial reductions can be achieved in damage equivalent rotor shaft and drive train loads in wind turbines with bend-twist coupled blades. Contrary to SWT simulations, results of PHATAS simulations show that damage equivalent shaft torque decreases when the bending-twisting coupling is increased through the use of higher fiber angle in the spar cap plies. Reduction in damage equivalent shaft torque is important, because shaft torque enters the gear box which is one of the most susceptible components to fatigue damage in wind turbines.

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent bearing 1 loads	Axial Force x (N)	5875.2	5572.13	5143.12	5140.68	5409.6
	Shear Force y (N)	82176.1	80757.2	79364.4	79813.4	83409.4
	Shear Force z (N)	74979.2	74198.6	75217.9	75490.4	76133
Ratio of DEL	Axial Force x		0.95	0.88	0.87	0.92
	Shear Force y		0.98	0.97	0.97	1.02
DE Bend-twist DE GFRP_1	Shear Force z		0.99	1.00	1.01	1.02

Table 7: Damage equivalent main bearing 1 loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta = 5^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent bearing 1 loads	Axial Force x (N)	5875.2	5007	5176.9	5242.6	5014.0
	Shear Force y (N)	82176.1	77480.4	75391.7	79796.7	78740.2
	Shear Force z (N)	74979.2	72557.4	71818.1	73690.8	73529.7
Ratio of DEL	Axial Force x		0.85	0.88	0.89	0.85
	Shear Force y		0.94	0.92	0.97	0.96
DE Bend-twist DE GFRP_1	Shear Force z		0.97	0.96	0.98	0.98

Table 8: Damage equivalent main bearing 1 loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta = 15^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent gearbox connection loads	Moment x (Nm)	5309.9	5408.46	6084.26	6023.65	5221.47
	Moment y (Nm)	6973.5	6940.36	7019.44	7040.07	7102.7
	Moment z (Nm)	6857.8	6766.1	6669.19	6699.15	6980.84
	Shear Force y (N)	8859.9	8746.21	8645.67	8685.85	9012.83
	Shear Force z (N)	8835.7	8798.31	8892.52	8921.51	9014.94
Ratio of DEL	Moment x		1.02	1.15	1.13	0.98
	Moment y		1.00	1.01	1.01	1.02
DE Bend-twist DE GFRP_1	Moment z		0.99	0.97	0.98	1.02
	Shear Force y		0.99	0.98	0.98	1.02
	Shear Force z		1.00	1.01	1.01	1.02

Table 9: Damage equivalent main shaft gearbox connection loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta = 5^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent gearbox connection loads	Moment x (Nm)	5309.9	5722.2	6738.85	6224.65	5565.9
	Moment y (Nm)	6973.5	6875.0	6872.5	6968.8	6946.5
	Moment z (Nm)	6857.8	6518.4	6347.9	6749.8	6627.1
	Shear Force y (N)	8859.9	8459.0	8252.8	8754.4	8580.0
	Shear Force z (N)	8835.7	8684.8	8651.6	8789.5	8777
Ratio of DEL	Moment x		1.08	1.27	1.17	1.05
	Moment y		0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00
DE Bend-twist DE GFRP_1	Moment z		0.95	0.93	0.98	0.97
	Shear Force y		0.95	0.93	0.99	0.97
	Shear Force z		0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99

Table 10: Damage equivalent main shaft gearbox connection loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades – (SWT results / $\theta = 15^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) rotor and drive train root loads	Rotor shaft – Torque (Nm)	14755	14249	15992	15590	14251
	Rotor shaft – Yawing Moment (Nm)	489564	451224	410254	411553	458578
	Rotor – Tilting moment (Nm)	478204	436125	397560	400927	442377
	Drive train – Tilting Moment (Nm)	350081	335140	315758	317138	344271
	Drive train – Yawing Moment (Nm)	345501	325322	307035	307782	331387
	Rotor – Axial aero force (N)	16001	15249	15202	15146	15103
	Drive train – Lateral force (N)	6266	6193	6189	6164	6312
	Drive train – Vertical force (N)	5119	4951	4919	4901	4978
Ratio of DEL	Rotor shaft – Torque		0.97	1.08	1.06	0.97
	Rotor shaft – Yawing Moment		0.92	0.84	0.84	0.94
	Rotor – Tilting moment		0.91	0.83	0.84	0.93
	Drive train – Tilting Moment		0.96	0.90	0.91	0.98
	Drive train – Yawing Moment		0.94	0.89	0.89	0.96
DE Bend – twist DE GFRP_1	Rotor – Axial aero force		0.96	0.95	0.95	0.94
	Drive train – Lateral force		0.99	0.99	0.98	1.01
	Drive train – Vertical force		0.97	0.96	0.96	0.97

Table 11: Damage equivalent rotor shaft and drive train loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades^b – (PHATAS results / $\theta=5^\circ$)

Wind turbine with blade configuration		GFRP_1	GFRP_2	HGCFRP_2	HGCFRP_3	HGCFRP_5
Damage equivalent (DE) rotor and drive train root loads	Rotor shaft – Torque (Nm)	14755	13739	14923	13679	13377
	Rotor shaft – Yawing Moment (Nm)	489564	404283	347117	364641	404435
	Rotor – Tilting moment (Nm)	478204	395145	336993	362751	392681
	Drive train – Tilting Moment (Nm)	350081	311968	277539	291703	313709
	Drive train – Yawing Moment (Nm)	345501	302939	270462	282443	304938
	Rotor – Axial aero force (N)	16001	14471	14352	14314	14432
	Drive train – Lateral force (N)	6266	5835	5709	5760	5939
	Drive train – Vertical force (N)	5119	4802	4594	4692	4755
Ratio of DEL	Rotor shaft – Torque		0.93	1.01	0.93	0.91
	Rotor shaft – Yawing Moment		0.83	0.71	0.74	0.83
	Rotor – Tilting moment		0.83	0.70	0.76	0.82
	Drive train – Tilting Moment		0.89	0.79	0.83	0.90
	Drive train – Yawing Moment		0.88	0.78	0.82	0.88
DE Bend – twist DE GFRP_1	Rotor – Axial aero force		0.90	0.90	0.89	0.90
	Drive train – Lateral force		0.93	0.91	0.92	0.95
	Drive train – Vertical force		0.94	0.90	0.92	0.93

Table 12: Damage equivalent rotor shaft and drive train loads for turbines with GFRP and hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades^b – (PHATAS results / $\theta=15^\circ$)

For the wind turbine with the bend-twist coupled blade HGCFRP_3, Figure 5 compares the shaft torque of the wind turbine having blades with 15° spar cap ply angle with the shaft torque of the wind turbine having blades with 5° spar cap ply angle. As seen in Fig.5, for the 15° fiber angle case, the range of the fluctuation of the shaft torque is less than the 5° fiber angle case. Hence, for the wind turbine with the blade HGCFRP_3, 7% reduction in damage equivalent shaft torque is achieved compared to the wind turbine with the baseline blade GFRP_1. Overall evaluation of the damage equivalent loads calculated by PHATAS in the blade root, in the rotor and in the drive train shows that in general, higher reductions in fatigue damage equivalent loads can be achieved by the use of hybrid GFRP and CFRP bend-twist coupled blades in wind turbines compared to the use of full GFRP blades.

Figure 5: Variation of shaft torque in the wind turbine with the bend-twist coupled blade HGCFRP_3

Except for the damage equivalent shaft torque (moment x) calculated by SWT, both SWT and PHATAS simulations show that reduction in fatigue damage equivalent loads in the wind turbine system is higher when the bending-twisting coupling is increased through the use of higher fiber angle in the spar cap plies. Figure 6 compares the element-average fiber direction stresses in the upper face of the finite elements in the baseline blade GFRP_1 and in the bend-twist coupled blade GFRP_2. The stress plots are recovered via superelement restitution in SWT at the time when there exists a local peak in the flapwise bending moment at the root of the blade. As shown in Fig. 6, for both blades maximum fiber direction stress occurred at the junction of the transition region of the blade and the DU40_A17 airfoil. Figure 6 shows that there is %5.5 reduction in the maximum fiber direction stress in the bend-twist coupled blade GFRP_2 compared to the baseline blade GFRP_1.

Figure 6: Comparison of average fiber direction stresses in the upper faces of the elements (Pa)

When SWT and PHATAS results are assessed together in terms of reduction in damage equivalent loads, bend-twist coupled blade HGCFRP_3 stands out as the best solution. It is recommended that to have more clear understanding of the damage equivalent load results obtained by SWT and by PHATAS, wind turbine simulations be carried out for different turbulent wind profiles and obtain average values of damage equivalent loads as indicated by IEC 61400-1. Such a study can shed more light on some of the differences in the damage equivalent loads obtained by SWT and PHATAS, especially in the shaft torque.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The use of different off-axis ply angles in the main spar caps of wind turbine blades is investigated for its effectiveness in reducing fatigue damage equivalent loads in the whole wind turbine system. Study is conducted utilizing both linear and non-linear blade models in the multi-body models of the 5MW wind turbine system that are set up in SWT and PHATAS. Results obtained by the SWT and the PHATAS simulations show that in the overall, with the introduction of off-axis CFRP spar cap plies in the blades, higher reductions in the damage equivalent loads can be achieved in the wind turbine systems compared to the baseline turbine system with the baseline GFRP blade. Except for the damage equivalent shaft torque calculated by SWT, both SWT and PHATAS simulations also show that reduction in fatigue damage equivalent loads in the wind turbine system is higher when the bending-twisting coupling is increased through the use of higher fiber angle in the spar cap plies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the METU Center for Wind Energy and the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK), Project No: 213M611.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Jonkman, S. Butterfield, W. Musial and G. Scott, *Definition of a 5-MW Reference Wind Turbine Offshore System Development*, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, NREL/TP-500-38060, 2009.
- [2] X. Zhou, L. An and Z. Wang, Twist-Bend Coupling Analysis for 5 MW Wind Turbine Blades, *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, **152-154**, 2012, pp. 703-708.
- [3] H.J. Lin and W.M. Lai, A Study of Elastic Coupling to the Wind Turbine Blade by Combined Analytical and Finite Element Beam Model, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **44(23)**, 2010, pp. 2643-2665.
- [4] D.W. Lobitz, P.S.Veers, G.R. Eisler, D.J. Laino, P.G. Migliore, and G. Bir, The Use of Twist-coupled Blades to Enhance the Performance of Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines, SAND2001-1303, Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, USA, 2001.
- [5] M. Capellaro, Design Limits of Bend Twist Coupled Wind Turbine Blades, *53rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, AIAA 2012-1501, 2012, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.
- [6] M.O. Gözcü, M.N. Olgun and A. Kayran, Investigation of the effect of off-axis spar cap plies on damage equivalent loads in wind turbines with superelement blade definition, *AIAA Science and Technology Forum and Exposition 2014, Gaylord National Resort & Convention Center, 13-17 January 2014, National Harbor, MD, USA*, Paper AIAA 2014-1223, 2014.
- [7] M.O. Gözcü, and A. Kayran, Investigation of the effect of bending-twisting coupling on the load in wind turbines with superelement blade definition, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **524** 012040, 2014, (doi:10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012040).
- [8] M.O. Gözcü, T. Farsadi, Ö. Şener, and A. Kayran, Assessment of the Effect of Hybrid GFRP-CFRP Usage in Wind Turbine Blades on the Reduction of Fatigue Damage Equivalent Loads in the Wind Turbine System, *AIAA Science and Technology Forum and Exposition, AIAA SciTech 2015, 33rd Wind Energy Symposium, 5-9 January 2015, Kissimmee, Florida, USA*, Paper AIAA 2015-0999, 2015.
- [9] Samcef Wind Turbines (SWT) User Help, V.3.3, Siemens Inc., p.87, p. 154, pp. 234-236, 2013.
- [10] C. Lindenburg., PHATAS Release “JAN-2012a” Users Manual, Program for Horizontal Axis wind Turbine Analysis and Simulation, ECN-I--05-005 r10, 2012.
- [11] B.J. Jonkman, TurbSim User’s Guide: Version 1.50, NREL/TP-500-46198, September 2009.
- [12] D.Winkelaar, SWIFT Program for Three-Dimensional Wind Simulation Part 1: Model Description and Program Verification, ECN-R-92-013, December 1992.
- [13] W.Yu, VABS Manual for Users, last accessed date: 23.03.2015, <http://analyswift.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/VABS-Manual.pdf>, 2011.